

SIMON: asSisted Mobility for Older aNd impaired users

Eva Muñoz^{1*}, Manuel Serrano¹, Antonio Marqués¹, Marcus Handte², Stephan Wagner²

1. ETRA Investigación y Desarrollo, Spain

* Avda. Tres Forques 147, 46014 Valencia (Spain), +34 963 134 082, emunoz.etraid@grupoetra.com

2. Locoslab GmbH, Germany

Abstract

SIMON is a demonstration project with three large-scale pilots in Madrid, Lisbon and Parma aiming to use ICT services to promote the independent living and societal participation of mobility-impaired people in the context of on-street public parking areas and multiple transport modes. The project tackles two main challenges:

- Reduction of fraud by demonstrating the use of an ICT-enhanced European Disable Badge for public parking, on the basis of physical –i.e. smartcards - and virtual access right tokens –i.e. e-access through mobile devices.
- Proposal of specific multimodal navigation solutions for elderly and disabled people, using Open Data hubs and pre-existing toolsets that will be populated and exploited with specific information – e.g. elevators located near sub-way stations.

An additional challenge is the instantiation of a proven methodology for data privacy preservation and authentication of users.

Keywords:

Mobility, Disabled, ICT

Introduction

SIMON is an EC funded demonstration project (CIP-ICT-PSP-2013-7-621041) with three large-scale pilots in Madrid, Lisbon and Parma aiming to use ICT services to promote the independent living and societal participation of mobility-impaired people in the context of on-street public parking areas and multiple transport modes.

The project tackles two main challenges: reduction of fraud in the pre-ICT implementation of the European Disable Badge for public parking areas, and the proposal of specific multimodal navigation solutions for elderly and people with disabilities.

Both cases require extensive integration of multiple databases with dedicated personal information. Thus, an additional challenge the project has to assume is the instantiation of a proven methodology for data privacy preservation and authentication of users.

This paper describes the work done in the first half of the project and details different phases completed to achieve the most challenging stage in the project: the starting of the piloting with real users under real-world conditions. In addition, we introduce the group of services and applications that the project has delivered to address the challenges introduced previously. Together, these services and applications are forming the reference architecture for the current pilot in Madrid, Lisbon and Parma as well as future deployments of the SIMON system.

Motivation

In the last years, the urban population has been growing dramatically. In 2008, for the first time, half of the world inhabitants lived in urban area. Moreover, recent studies expect that about 66% of the people would be urbanites in 2050 [1]. These percentages grow even bigger when focusing on developed countries and regions such as Europe, one of the most densely populated areas in the world. At the same time, the world population is growing faster and faster and in many countries, the population is aging rapidly. Due to these developments, there is a considerable number of people with reduced mobility capabilities [2] and, as a result, providing tools to improve the personal mobility of mobility-impaired persons is a key issue to tackle in many societies.

Since mobility is fundamental to enhance the inclusion in the community and because mobility-impaired persons and their families are often dependent on public transport, in the European Union (EU), mobility has long been at the core of EU policy strategies, both at private level and through public transport.

The SIMON European project aims at developing a solution that provides integrated services and applications that enhance the mobility of impaired users as part of the overall transport network. The development of this solution requires the development of several novel services and applications that improve the mobility experience. However, to offer and test this mobility experience in large-scale real-world settings, it is necessary to establish smart connections to the existing services that already manage the different parts of the transport network in the city.

With its novel services and applications, the SIMON project aims at accomplishing two main goals. Firstly, the reduction of fraud in the pre-ICT implementation of the European Disable Badge for public parking areas. Reducing this fraud can greatly improve the experience of mobility-impaired users since more free spaces are available to those who actually need them. Secondly, the proposal of specific multimodal navigation solutions that connect the available data sources across different owners throughout a city in order to provide an integrated system that can address the specific needs of mobility-impaired users.

The potential users of the SIMON platform are:

- Citizens that want to plan their trips seamlessly across public and private modes of transport. To them, SIMON offers multimodal navigation with step-by-step guidance and real-time information about public transport options, parking areas and transport network incidents.
- Mobility impaired persons who are legitimate holders of a European Disabled Badge and want to exercise the associated rights. To them, SIMON offers a usable ICT integration that reduces the fraudulent use of the European Disabled Badge and thus, increases the availability of reserved resources.
- Public authorities that manage the use of the public space for parking purposes. To them, SIMON offers information on the use of the public parking areas, thereby, enabling the establishment of policies promoting the sustainable use of all modes of transports.
- Public Transport Operators and Parking Facilities Managers that want to support the European Disabled Badge to improve their services. To them, SIMON offers an integrated solution to enhance their payment and access right gateways. Moreover, SIMON enables them to publish real-time information about their services such that it becomes available to the citizens during trip planning and navigation.

The approach and the architecture

SIMON builds on existing mobility services and adds the required integration work to provide a seamless services integration layer which can be instantiated in different cities according to the specific context and the services available.

To instantiate its ICT services, SIMON adopts an implementation approach which ensures the integration of access rights management to public parking spaces with the technology available in each site, and the different available public transport modes, etc. and ensures transferability across Europe, not imposing constraints to the already existing policies.

This is achieved by means of:

- An Open Architecture to be used by any authority or service provider willing to deploy SIMON approach. This architecture has been applied in each pilot site as the umbrella for the services to be provided.
- Four independent service platforms – SIMON SAYS, SIMON ANSWERS, SIMON BOOKS and SIMON OPENS - that are instantiated at each pilot site based on the specific context and maturity of the currently running services, interfacing the current existing IT infrastructure and complementing it.
- The use of a common set of applications: SIMON LEADS, a mobile application addressing the citizens as end-users of SIMON; SIMON CONTROLS, a mobile application for the parking controllers in the pilot sites; and finally SIMON backoffice,

SIMON: asSisted MObility for Older aNd impaired users

an IT framework to support public authorities and transport operators to manage the services proposed by the project.

The use of standards and accessible technology as security tokens to fight fraud: SMART CARDS, SMART PHONES and SMART PARK METERS.

Some adaptors have been developed to connect the external elements –park meters, systems to detect the access to restricted areas – to the services, as well as data adaptors serve to get the information from several sources: static parking and restricted data, and other external sources in general. All data types form the City Data Repository where SIMON centralized information is stored.

The blocks used to define SIMON architecture are shown in Figure 1

Figure 1 – SIMON Architecture diagram

SIMON Services Envisaged Usage and Users Added Value

The SIMON system is a platform supporting some services that feed different applications, all of them accessible through mobile devices. A backoffice also provides the access through a web application to manage the whole system. From an ICT point of view, SIMON services will be adaptable to heterogeneous environment, with different capabilities. Following, the different services implemented in SIMON are described.

SIMON SAYS

In order to fight fraud, SIMON proposes a security challenge service to verify the identity of the user access rights to dedicated public parking spaces. Thus, in the context of the project SIMON SAYS exclusively focuses on reducing the misuse of the European disable parking badge by non-authorized people.

Fraud fighting has been introduced at two levels: On the one hand, at Detection level, through the use of smart cards that will help parking controllers identifying fraudulent badges, or through plate recognition systems. On the other hand, at Prevention level, through the use of the SIMON SAYS service.

SIMON ANSWERS

SIMON wrappers current available data silos in order to make them available to the SIMON applications – notably to the SIMON LEADS mobile app. An instance of the semantic data linker and processing engine in use by the Public Bus Transport Operator of Madrid (EMT-Madrid) in the context of the FP7 GAMBAS project [4] has been deployed in all three pilot sites. This solution enables the seamless linking of different data sources, offering an easy and powerful toolset for the development of specific graphical user interfaces for navigation. The data hubs are provided by each of the pilot sites, and in particular it is pretty important the information provided through the disabled and elderly associations involved at SIMON user group.

SIMON ANSWERS provides the functions to enable multi-modal navigation within the target cities. To provide these functions, SIMON ANSWERS exposes several service endpoints to the citizen's app, SIMON LEADS, which can be grouped logically into three main groups:

- Geographic services, which enable the users to explore the target city using an interactive map-based visualization. Thereby, the visualization supports both, outdoor and indoor environments. For SIMON LEADS indoor environments are particularly relevant in cases where users are travelling using a subway or a train as this may entail complex navigation inside a subway or train station. As an innovative feature, SIMON ANSWERS provides not only navigation instructions in outdoor settings but also is able to provide navigation instructions in indoor environments.
- Navigation services, aiming at enabling seamless navigation in the target city by means of SIMON LEADS. The technical basis for this is the computation of (accessible) routes using different modes of transportation. The targeted modes thereby cover driving (in a private car), transit (using the public transport means available in the target city) and walking. For the latter, SIMON ANSWERS provides routes for outdoor environments and indoor environments alike. The basis for route computation is an object model to represent routes using segments.
- Information services, which provide additional information to SIMON LEADS that can be accessed via the information screen. The information that is available via

SIMON: asSisted MobIlity for Older aNd impaired users

information services will depend on the target city but the core services can be used to provide generic information will work across all target cities. The five generic services that have been implemented so far provide endpoints for transit network information (stops, lines, schedules, incidents) and parking information (parking places)

SIMON BOOKS

In the context of assisted mobility, introducing the functionality of a booking service for parking areas or even limiting its availability to mobility impaired users will have a nice impact on the quality of life and mobility experience of SIMON users.

In SIMON, the main strategy to be deployed after instantiating this service consists on providing information on occupancy levels and prediction of occupancy to feed the SIMON ANSWERS navigation service.

SIMON OPENS

This service is an adaptation of the access-control mechanisms in order to authenticate the owner of an EU disabled card who is driving into a urban area with a limited access. . The main functionality that SIMON OPENS offers is the seamless mobility experience for the user of a SIMON access-rights token, since, with the very same security “key”, the citizen will be able to use reserved parking spots and access freely to urban controlled areas.

The citizen mobile app

SIMON LEADS is the mobile app that provides multimodal navigation functionality for mobility impaired users and for holders of disabled parking cards, it allows the validation of parking spots and requesting of access to access-restricted areas.

The functions provided can be grouped into three categories, namely:

- Navigation: The navigation functions of SIMON LEADS enable mobility-impaired persons to navigate through the target cities in a multi-modal and adaptive manner, meaning that the routes computed for them consider their mobility preferences as well as their specific mobility restrictions (e.g. wheelchair accessible), etc.
- Information: In addition to navigation, SIMON LEADS provide mobility-related information which contains schedule information, incident information as well as accessibility information such as the location of elevators in subway stations, or the location of disabled parking spots, for example.
- Validation: Last but not least, the application support the fighting of fraud situations related to the disabled badges by integrating the mechanisms to enable the validation of badges, e.g. in order to indicate that a user is using a disabled parking spot or to acquire access to a restricted area.

Being the application targeted towards the (mobility-impaired) end-users, special care has been taken to make it accessible to users with different impairments. Towards this end, the

SIMON: asSisted MobIlity for Older aNd impaired users

development process closely followed and adhered to the Accessibility Guidelines published by the Android developers [4]. In addition, the SIMON consortium executed a number of focus group tests with disabled users to ensure that the application concepts are easy to understand and their implementation is easy to use. Figure 2 shows two screens of the app: (a) for selecting a route, it offers different options to the user, and (b) shows in a map different icons related to mobility: bus stops (yellow), parking reserved to disabled (green) and an accessible entrance to a metro station (blue).

Figure 2 – SIMON mobile app (a): route selection (b) exploring in a map

The SIMON Backoffice: a tool for the city policy maker

The SIMON BACKOFFICE application provides support to the SIMON SAYS, SIMON OPENS, and SIMON BOOKS services, actually implementing the software functionality of the services, supporting the data management and persistence, and the interaction with the local systems that control park meters and access controlled areas. Figure 3 shows an example of use of SIMON Backoffice.

Figure 3 Authority operator application status of parking spaces map

Testing with users: the small scale pilot

The last phase in the work in progress has been related with the first testing with users. A small scale pilot took place in the three cities participating in the project, where some selected users had the opportunity of doing a validation of the first prototype. They offered a real valuable feedback that was analysed to detect different performance issues, as well to improve some aspects of usability and design. On summer 2015, we can say that the new enhanced app is ready to start the large scale pilot that will last until the end of the project.

SIMON services have been deployed in the three specific pilot sites –Madrid, Lisbon and Parma-, with existing initiatives running and special features that complement each other to provide a global solution. Whilst the services identified by SIMON are common to the architecture, and therefore to each of the test sites, the services already deployed in each pilot covering the basic functionalities for parking management and control and navigation information have different implementations.

Scenarios and use cases

In the context of architecture and design, a use case is basically a description of a set of interactions between the system and one or more actors (either a user or another system). A scenario is a broader and more encompassing description of a user's interaction with the system, rather than a path through a use case. In SIMON, several key scenarios have been identified that have helped us to make decisions about the architecture.

An example of use case that will be demonstrated in SIMON is the “CITIZEN IDENTIFICATION AT A PARKING SPACE USING NFC SMART PHONE AND A RFID (NFC) EU BADGE”. In this use case, the citizen uses his NFC smart phone to be identified in the parking area with interaction with the RFID badge attached to his windscreen. In the Table 1, the different elements used to describe the use case are shown.

Trigger:	The citizen parks at reserved parking space. The citizen wants to validate the parking.
Preconditions:	<p>The citizen must have an Android smart phone with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NFC technology available and activated • Internet access (3G, WiFi) <p>The citizen has installed the SIMON app (SIMON LEADS) in his smart phone.</p> <p>The citizen is registered in the system and has logged in at the mobile app.</p> <p>The citizen must have a EU Badge adapted with RFID tag attached to the windscreen of his car.</p> <p>The system is able to communicate with the central database and offer updated response in real time.</p>
Post-conditions :	<p>The citizen has validated the parking.</p> <p>The citizen receives an electronic receipt in his smart phone</p> <p>When the citizen is validated, the system stores the information (OP_06).</p>
Normal Flow:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user is going to validate the parking space by placing the phone near the RFID sticker 2. The system recognizes the RFID tag and sends the challenge (e.g.: a word or a code) 3. The citizen enters the challenge in the application (SIMON SAYS) and validates the operation. 4. The system sends an electronic receipt of the operation to citizen’s smart phone.

Table 1 – Use case definition

Conclusions

The SIMON project aims at improving inclusion of mobility-impaired persons in their daily life by providing a set of ICT services that helps them to enhance their mobility. Towards this end, they can get access to personalized traveling information, for instance, through SIMON ANSWERS service or the SIMON LEADS application, which provide citizens with transport information adapted to their needs. Moreover, the SIMON approach to modernize the EU parking disable badge will foster a wider adoption of specific policies to support the disabled in the use of their own vehicles.

By facilitating the detection of fraudulent (uses of) disabled badges and the resulting reduction of fraud, the deployment of SIMON outcomes can have a direct positive impact on the city

SIMON: asSisted MobIlity for Older aNd impaired users

economy. This impact is achieved mainly through the enhancement of payment and access right gateways in public transport and parking facilities and by supporting the adoption of a common EU disable badge. The implementation of a security challenge service (SIMON SAYS) in the project allows the identity verification of the user rights to dedicated public parking spaces and specific city areas, while preserving privacy. In this case SIMON goes a step further delivering a robust tool against fraud.

The reference architecture, which has been defined in the first stage of the project, has been now deployed in the three pilot sites. Thus, we are confident that the SIMON approach can act as a reference for other cities as well.

Acknowledgement(S)

The authors would like to thank for their support the European Commission and the partners of the EU FP7 project SIMON.

References

1. [online] <http://www.un.org/en/development/desa/news/population/world-urbanization-prospects-2014.html>
2. EC. EUROSTAT EU-SILC UDB 2010. version 1 of March 2012
3. GAMBAS FP7 Project, <http://www.gambas-ict.eu/>
4. [online] <https://developer.android.com/guide/topics/ui/accessibility/index.html>
5. SIMON Project website: <http://77simon-project.eu>